

Artificial Intelligence in E-Commerce: A Comprehensive Analysis Combining Bibliometric Evaluation and TCCM Framework

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ABSTRACT

AI can be integrated into e-commerce platforms to support marketing, sales, supply chain management, and decision-making processes. AI provides real-time data to e-commerce platforms, making it easier to understand what buyers want. The goal of the study is to review the body of knowledge on artificial intelligence in e-commerce through bibliometric analysis and theories, characteristics, context, and methodologies (TCCM) framework. Citation analysis, co-citation analysis, and co-occurrence of keywords are used in bibliometric analysis, whereas the TCCM framework categorised the literature into theory, characteristics, context, and methodology. The study identified the most well-known authors, papers, journals, and nations in this field, as well as the most co-cited writers, using a bibliometric analysis of 112 research articles that were taken from the WoS database between 2003 and 2023. The bibliometric analysis also revealed that trust, machine learning, personalisation, and recommender systems are the main areas of focus for artificial intelligence research in e-commerce. The theories used in the chosen articles are grouped into seven pertinent categories, some of which are adoption and trust-related theories, while other themes include outcome factors, mediators, and moderators. In order to help direct future research into underrepresented issues and novel subjects that are anticipated to be significant, the report offers ideas for further study.

INTRODUCTION

E-commerce is a strategy facilitated by information exchange technology to execute business operations (Holsapple & Singh, 2000). E-commerce facilitators such as internet, payment gateway and analytics are pushing the world into e-commerce (Jain et al., 2021). The e-business practices are rapidly evolving and deeply penetrating with increased rates of adoption. This rapid development forces the firms to constantly adapt to the dynamic consumer needs (Bawack et al., 2022). This technological development has reached the stage of Artificial Intelligence. The term "artificial intelligence" (AI) refers to the capacity of a

computer or a robot controlled by a computer to do tasks that are typically performed by humans because they call for human intelligence and discernment (Kumari, 2021). AI eliminates the possibility of subjective judgement by processing information more quickly and in greater volume than humans, leading to more effective conclusions. Use of AI in E-commerce platforms helps customers to save time, easier product and price comparisons, access to wide range of products and available 24*7 (Fedorko et al., 2022). AI in E-commerce helps in building a sizable customer base, attempting to understand the customer wants, conducting real-time research, developing the best possible solutions, and performing a variety of other tasks (Soni, 2020).

The domain is being researched from past three decades and records contribution from articles across various disciplines. The stream of constantly evolving AI demands for persistent research and literature synthesis for systematic exploration of the domain. The field still witnesses the absence of insights into unexplored areas of this domain. (Bawack et al., 2022) conducted bibliometric analysis extracted data from WoS from 1975 -2020, the world witnessed a pandemic later which drastically shifted the world to the online platform. A large number of literatures were published post this period. Most of the review studies were in context of AI or E-commerce solely. (Anayat & Rasool, 2024) conducted bibliometric analysis on AI but in marketing context as a whole. Very few studies have conducted bibliometric analysis on AI in E-commerce including a systematic literature review. Thus, further research is needed for a comprehensive overview of AI in E-commerce. This study aims to fill the gap with thorough evaluation combining bibliometric analysis techniques with various framework, tool and methods through TCCM analysis. The paper aims to identify trends, clusters and future research directions by formulation the following research questions (RQ):

RQ1. What is the trend of publication in the field of AI in E-commerce?

RQ2. Which key concepts and trending keywords being studied in the domain?

RQ3. What is the intellectual structure of knowledge base of AI in E-commerce?

RQ4. What are the prominent theories, contexts, characteristics and methodologies employed to suggest future research directions?

The research findings show that AI in E-commerce primarily focuses on adoption of AI and trust on automated systems. The main research themes are adoption, trust, machine learning

and chatbots. The study contributes to the scholarly debate on AI applications in E-commerce. No study currently evaluates AI in E-commerce using a combination of bibliometric and systematic literature review. The study proposes potential research paradigms for future work classified on the basis of framework, context and methods making it easier for researchers to identify future research areas.

The remaining sections are stated as follows. The methodology section presents the data extraction criteria of the study using PRISMA approach. It is followed by bibliometric analysis and content analysis section. The study concludes in a discussion part, which is followed by sections on limitations and future research, implications, and conclusions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study the emergence of AI in E-commerce is studied using the bibliometric technique. Bibliometric analysis tool provides quantitative insights into the existing literature and analyse the bibliographic data to evaluate the contribution of authors, journals and institutions in a specific research area (Hassan & Loebbecke, 2017). The bibliometric method of review is classified into three i.e., performance analysis, science mapping and network analysis (Donthu et al., 2021). we employed performance analysis and science mapping for identification of the global trends and advancements in the field of AI and E-commerce.

We conducted citation analysis for performance analysis and keyword co-occurrence analysis and co-citation analysis for science mapping. Citation analysis was done using biblioshiny ensuring the selection of articles based on the threshold of at least 1 citation. For keyword co-occurrence analysis VOS viewer was used keeping the threshold of minimum 2 occurrences. VOS viewer was also used for co-citation analysis keeping the threshold of more than 10 citations. The study is based on Aria and Cuccrullo (2017) approach for conducting the bibliometric analysis. This approach is organized and divided into three phases: data collection, data analysis and data visualisation and reporting to identify the emerging themes to propose future research directions. Figure 1 shows the details of inclusion and exclusion in a PRISMA flowchart.

DATA COLLECTION

The stage of data collection involves querying, selecting and exporting data from the selected database. First the source from where literatures are to be extracted is chosen and this study has selected Web of Science database. Web of Science is an interdisciplinary database which

supports 256 disciplines. Web of Science database is preferred because of its cleaner data which avoids the chances of duplication as compared to Scopus database resulting to better bibliometric information (Aria et al., 2020). The query command was applied to the title, abstract and keywords to extract relevant documents from Wos is {Artificial Intelligence} AND {"e-commerce" or "electronic commerce" or "online commerce"}. Ultimately 112 documents were selected for the final analysis and interpretation. (Figure1)

Data analysis of this paper was done using *Bibliometrix*, the R package and VOS viewer. Both the software's are widely used for bibliometric analysis. The R package incorporates renowned bibliometric tools for citation analysis (Fosso Wamba, 2020). It was specifically used to analyse the sources and documents in the field of AI and e-commerce research. Whereas VOS viewer is used to visually represent the associated literatures. Software analyses the similarities and direct indirect links between literatures to construct a map and form clusters (Nees & Waltman, 2017).

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart of inclusion and exclusion criteria

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

3.1 Performance Analysis

The figure (2) represents year wise citation and publication performance of AI in E-commerce. A total of 112 articles belonging to the WoS database reveal that the publications have picked up pace after 2018. The field of AI and E-commerce has gained popularity due to evidences of successful applications of AI innovations in the business world. The research area is new and emerging because past 5 years constitutes of 94.64% of the total publications from 2019-2023 also disclosing the developing interest of the researchers in this field.

Figure 2. Publication and citation trend

Leading Journal

The most cited journals in the field of AI in E-commerce have been identified and presented in Table (1). *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research* emerged as the most prolific journal with a total of 16 publications followed by *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications* with 13 publications. One of the premier journals *Journal of Business research* ranks 5th in the top 10 journals with 5 publications and 121 citations. *Electronic Markets* published 5 articles in AI and E-commerce, their article by Adam M, 2021 had the most citations with 182 citations. To evaluate the journals average citation per item (ACI) was calculated and Table indicated *International Journal of Logistics management* has the highest ACI despite publishing only 3 articles. The number of publications indicate the productivity and the citations indicate the article quality and majority of the journals were ranked “A” or “B” by the Australian Business Deans Council.

JOURNAL	TOTAL PUBLICATION	TOTAL CITATION	ACI	MOST CITED ARTICLES	FRQ
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research	16	134	8.375	Lee Uk, 2022	22
Electronic Commerce Research and Applications	13	76	5.846154	Ngai Ewt, 2021	21
Electronic Commerce Research	8	14	1.75	Hsu Pf, 2021	
Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	6	218	36.33333	Nilashi M, 2015	75
Electronic Markets	5	404	80.8	Adam M, 2021	182
Journal of Business Research	5	121	24.2	Pizzi G, 2021	58
Industrial Marketing Management	3	110	36.67	Kumar B, 2020	46
International Journal of Logistics Management	3	121	40.33	Modigil S, 2022	86
Journal of Enterprise Information Management	3	43	14.33	Bedué P, 2022	29
European Journal of Marketing	2	23	11.5	Koponen Jp, 2020	20

Table 1. Top 10 Journals

Prolific Author

The most prolific authors in AI context were identified in E-commerce research (RQ1). Table (2) represents the top 8 authors who have published altogether 20 documents. Jian Mou being the most productive author with 5 publications and received 92 citations followed by Xusen Chang and Mengmeng Song with 3 publications each. Although, Martin Adam has only one publication but has received the highest citation of 182 citations. These authors belong to 6 countries, South Korea, China, Spain, India, Germany and Australia.

AUTHOR	NP	TC	H_INDEX	AFFILIATION
MOU J	5	92	3	Pusan National University
CHENG XS	3	45	2	Renmin University of China
SONG MM	3	50	2	Hainan University
XING XY	3	50	2	Hainan University
SAURA JR	2	9	2	Rey Juan Carols University
SHARMA S	2	5	2	Fortune Institute of International Business
ADAM M	1	182	1	Technical University of Darmstadt
ADAM MTP	1	5	1	University Of Newcastle

Table 2. Top 8 authors

Top Contributing Organizations

Table (3) depicts the most contributing universities in the article production in the field of AI and E-commerce. Pusan National University has the highest contribution with 6 articles followed by Complutense University of Madrid and Pennsylvania State University with 4 articles each. Rest other universities have contributed at least 3 articles in this area.

AFFILIATION	ARTICLES
Pusan National University	6
Complustense University of Madrid	4
Pennsylvania State University	4
Copenhagen Business School	3
Hamad Bin Khalifa University - Qatar	3
Hong Kong Baptist University	3
Indian Institute of Management (IIM System)	3
Pennsylvania Commonwealth of Higher Education	3
Pennsylvania State University- University Park	3
Universidade Do Algarve	3

Table 3. Publication and citation trend

Countries

Table (4) depicts the contribution of the different countries indicating China as the highest publishing country. China contributes 60 % of the total production in the area of AI and E-commerce. The next biggest contributing country is USA followed by India contributing 40% and 19% respectively. South Korea, Germany and Portugal also have significant contributions in the field of AI and E-commerce.

COUNTRY	FRQ
CHINA	68
USA	45
INDIA	22
SOUTH KOREA	21
GERMANY	14
PORTUGAL	13
SPAIN	13
UK	12
AUSTRALI	9
MALAYSIA	9

Table 4. Publication and citation trend

Most Cited Articles

The most prolific publications on AI and E-commerce in terms of the citations received are represented in Figure (3). The table indicates that Hoyer et al.'s (2020) article on the impact of new technologies on each stage of shopping journey is the most cited publication with 197 citations because the new age technologies include AI along with other innovations. The next most cited article "*AI Based Chatbots in Customer Service and Their Effects on User Compliance*" by Adam et al. received 182 citations. The article with minimum number of citations is "*The Role of Security, Design and Content Factors on Consumer Trust in Mobile Commerce*" by Nilashi et al. with 75 citations.

Figure 3. Publication and citation trend

3.2 SCIENCE MAPPING

Science mapping aims at studying the connections among different research topics (Donthu et al., 2021a). This process conducts a focused investigation of the intellectual relationships between different research topics. Keyword co-occurrence analysis and co-citation analysis are the two science mapping techniques used in this study.

3.2.1 Keyword Co-occurrences Analysis

Keyword co-occurrences analyse the literature and identify the relations between different themes and visually represent different research areas (Donthu et al., 2021). The items of the co-occurrences are taken from “author keywords” keeping the minimum number of co-occurrences 2 for each keyword. The keywords were manually filtered, and some were excluded, which were found to be irrelevant to the field of AI and E-commerce.

Cluster 1. Technology in 21st century	TO	TL	Cluster 2. AI in decision making	TO	TL
e-commerce	17	29	artificial intelligence	29	48
covid-19	6	10	Trust	15	16
digitalization	3	7	decision making	2	2
innovation	3	6	Risk	2	3
gender	2	4			

marketing	2	3			
network analysis	2	5			
supply chain management	2	4			
Cluster 3. AI in consumer service			Cluster 4. AI in data analytics		
perceived value	3	4	machine learning	8	15
customer experience	2	4	personalization	3	6
customer value	2	3	explainable intelligence	artificial	2 2
perceived privacy risk	2	3	recommender system	2	6
service quality	2	3	sentiment analysis	2	1
Cluster 5. AI in research			Cluster 6. AI in consumer behaviour		
bibliometric analysis	2	2	perceived anthropomorphism	2	5
privacy concerns	2	3	perceived intelligence	2	5
research agenda	2	3	purchase intelligence	2	7
Cluster 7. AI in communication			Cluster 8. AI in relationship management		
chatbot	5	7	relationship management	2	2
automation	2	3	social media	2	4
social presence	2	5			

Table 5. Keyword clusters

Cluster 1. Technology in 21st century

The keywords of cluster 1 depict the developments in the field of technology gradually. The period during covid and post covid witnessed the major growth in technology used in business and marketing. 24.24% of the total keywords is covered under cluster 1. E-commerce being the most used keyword of this cluster and has appeared in articles. The cluster has other dominated keyword that is E-commerce. All the keywords of this cluster focus on the technological developments through the century.

Figure 4. Keyword analysis through VOS viewer

Cluster 2 AI in Decision Making

Cluster 2 depicts the use of AI in Decision Making as all the keywords of the cluster are the factors that affect decision making. The cluster contains 12.12% of the total keywords and the highest occurring keyword i.e., “*Artificial Intelligence*” with 29 occurrences and 48 links. The most used keywords are “*Artificial Intelligence*” and “*Trust*” which has appeared.

Cluster 3 AI in Consumer Service

The third cluster contains 15.15% of the total keywords. The most occurred keyword of this cluster is “*Perceived Value*” but customer experience accompanies perceived value in highest link strength. The keywords of this cluster are customer centric and reveal that the cluster is focused towards the use of AI for enhancement of customer services and better customer experiences.

Cluster 4 AI in Data Analytics

The fourth cluster also contains 15.15% of the total keywords. The most dominant keyword of this cluster “*Machine Learning*” with 8 occurrences and 15 links. All the keywords of this

cluster point towards the use of AI in analysing the collected data. Data analysis builds a base for further actions.

Cluster 5 AI in Research

The fifth cluster contains 9.09% of the total keywords and the keywords specify its focus on AI related researches. Various methods are being used to conduct literature reviews one being bibliometric analysis to find new research agendas and gaps for further studies.

Cluster 6 AI in consumer Behaviour

The sixth cluster contains 9.09% of all the keywords. The keywords have occurred equal number of times but *Purchase Intention* having higher link strength than the other keywords. The keywords of this cluster imply that the researches were focused on interactions between AI and customers and their impact on customer behaviour.

Cluster 7 AI in Communication

The seventh cluster contains keywords related to communication to the customers such as chatbots. The keywords are focused towards uses of AI in effective and impactful communication to the consumers. The cluster contains 9.09% of the total keywords.

Cluster 8 AI in Relationship Management

The last cluster has two keywords forming 6.06% of the total keywords. The keywords specify the focus of cluster towards the management of relationship between the customer and the marketer by ensuring proper communication through different Medias.

3.2.2 Co- citation analysis

Co citation analysis is the other techniques used for intellectual relationship investigation with three objects of study namely author, journal and document. The object of our study was author co citation analysis. The main purpose if to depict the different research areas (Jeong et al. 2014). The study used VOS viewer for citation analysis with minimum citation criteria of more than 10 citations. The top authors based on citations are Venkatesh, Hair, Fornell, Davis and McKnight with a total of 169 citations altogether. VOS viewer gave an output with

four major clusters which is presented in Figure ... followed by a summary of all clusters.

Figure 5 Co- citation analysis through VOS viewer

Cluster 1: Artificial Intelligence Marketing: role

The cluster accumulates the contribution of 17 authors with a link strength of 2078. The authors of the cluster have discussed about different ways of application of AI in marketing. The authors have investigated customer responses and perceptions towards AI and their impact on various marketing aspects such as trust, engagement and purchase rate. However, the focal point of the cluster would remain *chatbots*. They have developed frameworks on implementation of AI in marketing based on the nature of service involved. They have analysed the response of customers and antecedents to their response. The authors suggested further investigation of AI characteristics and customers attributes to reveal the hidden potential of AI.

Cluster 2: Technology acceptance: Integration of Theories and Methodology

The second cluster contains 9 items with a link strength of. The authors of cluster conducted studies on development and extension of technology acceptance models and prominent methodologies applicable in evaluation of future models. The most cited paper of the cluster

is “USER ACCEPTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY: TOWARD A UNIFIED VIEW” in which the author compared eight models and their extensions to derive a unified model of information technology acceptance. Ferd D Davis developed a new scale for the most common variable for technology acceptance i.e., perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. The authors also focused on the methodologies mostly focusing on structural equation modelling. They recommended further investigation of externally controllable factors influencing the ease of use and usefulness of technology.

Cluster 3: AI and trust

The third cluster contains 6 items with total link strength of. The authors of the cluster focused on the trust and perceived risk by the consumer while using technology for commerce. The authors investigated various levels of trust and its impact on trust related behaviour. The authors also explored factors or antecedents of trust that build consumer trust in a non-human interaction environment and indirectly impact intention to use. David Gefen studied the role of trust on intention to use and TAM variables to conclude that PU will be affected by trust whereas PEOU will affect trust. The authors recommend to examine the moderating effects of trust on purchase intention since they have studied the direct effect of trust.

Cluster 4: Future Perspectives in Artificial Intelligence Research

The fourth cluster contains 5 items with total link strength of. The authors of this cluster have studied the technological and data driven innovations targeting better decision making and knowledge extraction. The data driven world call for efficient data management and analysis to identify potential opportunities and challenges. The authors highlight such opportunities, challenges of using AI and the coexistent threats and concerns of using AI. They also reviewed various procedural and statistical techniques used. The cluster focuses on depth reviews of the literatures to study the applied and potential uses of AI, methods of analysis being used and their impact on performance and major factors obstructing the achievement of goals. The authors recommended various research agendas for future research related to AI in various domains and different statistical remedies for different research domains.

CONTENT ANALYSIS

The researchers boost the bibliometric analysis of the study with a TCCM analysis. Within the framework, (T) represents theories, emphasizing the theoretical foundations; (C)

represents context or contextual factors, including geographic locations; and sectors, with (C) displaying the traits and (M) denoting approaches that focus on research designs and analysis.

Theories

The theoretical perspective of conceptualization of AI and E-commerce was analysed through various theories employed sample publications. Table (6) presents the prominent theories employed in this field. The domain acknowledges contribution from theories from different disciplines such as psychology and economics.

UTAUT model being the most employed theoretical framework which explains the adoption behaviour of users which is affected by performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating condition. Industries aim at understanding the adoption behaviour before application of AI to ensure customer retention. Other theories such as TAM, TRA and Theory of planned behaviour were also employed to study the adoption behaviour.

Social response theory brings out a new perspective of this domain. The theory provides evidences of individual biasness towards automated computers as social actors (NASS AND MOON 2000). The researches have highlighted the evidences of human rules application on anthropomorphic computers.

Trust transfer theory highlights the transfer of trust from recommended process to system. Trust is most researched aspect of this domain. Various other theories such as valance framework, automation of trust model have been employed to study the effects of trust on the AI and human interaction.

Various other theories such as expectation confirmation theory, privacy calculus theory and social presence theory provide insights into the stream. Though their have been various theoretical contributions to this domain new perspectives would still help in getting a deepening insight into the complexities of the domain.

THEORY	EXAMPLES	NUMBER OF ARTICLES S	ARTICLES
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Adoption Theories	UTAUT, Theory of reasoned action, theory of planned behaviour, TAM	16	Roh et al. (2023), de Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa (2023), Warner et al. (2022), Lee et al. (2022) Silva et al. (2023), Moriuchi, E. (2019)
Trust related theories	Trust Theory	5	Xu et al. (2023), Shareef et al. (2023), Bedué & Fritzsche (2022),
Social Psychology Theories	Social Exchange Theory	7	Shareef et al. (2023), Hsu et al. (2021), Nguyen at el. (2022), Dinh & Park (2023), Xu et al. (2023)
Social Group Theories	Media Richness Theory, Social Presence Theory, Social Support Theory	5	Malhotra & Ramalingam (2023), Sivathanu et al. (2023), Dinh & Park (2023), Koponen & Rytsy (2020)
Information Related Theories	Privacy Theory, Information Manipulation Theory	3	Luo et al. (2023), Kim et al. (2023), Sivanthanu et al. (2023)
Cognitive Theories	Expectation Confirmation Theory, Schema Theory	3	Silva et al. (2023), Brill et. al (2020), Pizzi et al. (2021), Guo &Jiang (2023)
Economic Theories	International Trade Theory, Agency Theory of Agglomeration	3	Qi et al. (2023), Salminen et al. (2022), Lin & Li (2023)
Other Theories	TOE, Social Response Thory	7	Sharma et al. (2022), Nayal et al. (2022), Cheng et al. (2021), Adam et al. (2021), Song et al. (2022)

Table 6. Prominent Theories

Context

Context refers to the circumstances or setting in which a specific study was carried out (Paul et al., 2017). Table (7) represents the countries and table (8) represents the industries where AI applications in E-commerce have been explored. The researchers concluded from the sample publications that most researches were based on single country. China being the most exploring country followed by USA and Brazil. In terms of industries studies mostly focused on services rather than manufacturing. The most explored industry being tourism & hospitality sector and SME's whereas the most unexplored sector being the fashion and agriculture. The industry-based researches open avenues for future exploration.

COUNTRY	FRQ	Articles
Bangladesh	1	(Shareef et al., 2023)
China	10	(Qin & Jiang., 2019; Asante et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2023; Cheng et al., 2022; Deng et al., 2023; B. Li et al., 2023; L. Li et al., 2023; Lin & Li, 2023; Luo et al., 2023; Roh et al., 2023)
USA	4	(Brill et. al.,2020; Moriuchi, E., 2019; Kim et al., 2023; Ortega & Lucia-Palacios, 2023)
Brazil	3	(Matuszelanski & Kopczewska., 2022; Rohden & Zeferino, 2023)
India	2	(Malhotra & Ramalingam, 2023; Pattanaik et al., 2021)
Germany	2	(Adam et. al., 2021; Saleem et al., 2023)
Spain	2	(de Andres-Sanchez & Gene-Albesa, 2023; Yoon & Lee, 2021)
Singapore	1	(Kim et al., 2023)
Portugal	1	(F. A. Silva et al., 2023)
Malaysia	1	(Rahman et. al., 2021)
Vietnam	1	(Nguyen et al., 2022)
Romania	1	(Nichifor et al., 2021)
Taiwan	1	(Hasiao et al., 2019)
Hong Kong	1	(Chow et al., 2023)
Poland	1	(Dymitrowski & Mielcarek., 2021)

Table 7. Countries

INDUSTRY	FRQ	CITATION
Tourism & Hospitality	4	(Cheng, Zhang, et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2023; Yoon & Lee, 2021)
SME	3	(Saleem et al., 2023; Sharma et al., 2022; Wei & Pardo, 2022)
Footwear	2	(S. C. Silva et al., 2023; Yoon & Lee, 2021)
Telecommunication	2	(B. Li et al., 2023; Pizzi et al., 2021)
Banking	2	(Rahman et al., 2021; Adam et al., 2021)
Transport	2	(Kiani Mavi et al., 2022; Hasiao et al., 2019)
Retail	2	(Behera et al., 2022; Nichifor et al., 2021)
Medical Consultation	2	(Luo et al., 2023; Pattanaik et al., 2021)
Fashion	1	(E. S. Silva & Bonetti, 2021)
Agriculture	1	(Lin & Li, 2023)
S-Commerce	1	(Leong et al., 2023)
Others	4	(de Andres-Sanchez & Gene-Albesa, 2023; Pizzi et al., 2021; Qi et al., 2023; Roh et al., 2023)

Table 8. Industries

Characteristics

Independent variable

The authors investigated the independent variables of the sample publications and found that the key focus was on AI attributes related factors. Those include variables of UTAUT model, perceived usefulness, perceived anthropomorphism, chatbot attributes, perceived warmth, perceived competence, AI information quality, e service quality and perceived intelligence. (Malhotra & Ramalingam, 2023) found that anthropomorphized products affect the purchase intention through AI whereas (Moussawi et al., 2021) confirmed that anthropomorphism is a crucial antecedent of adoption of AI. (Roh et al., 2023) also studies the adoption behaviour but using the variable of UTAUT model and theory of reasoned actions. (de Andres-Sanchez & Gene-Albesa, 2023) found that Enhancing chatbots' usability, building user trust, and boosting societal acceptance are critical to their acceptance as a technology. The second most prominent variable group was found to be trust related variables which included perceived trust, security, perceived risk and perceived privacy. The significant impact of trust on

behavioural intentions was confirmed by (de Andres-Sanchez & Gene-Albesa, 2023; Kim et al., 2023) other researched variable group were AI type related which studied the various types of AI used in E-commerce and consumer related variables which included variables such as attitude, social influence and expectations of the consumers. (Table 9)

Dependent variables

The authors investigated the independent variables of the sample publications and found that the key focus was on intention and engagement related variables. This group included variables such as Adoption, behavioural intention, engagement, word of mouth, purchase intention and online shopping intention. The researchers studied the direct as well as indirect effect of variables on the behavioural intention of the users (F. A. Silva et al., 2023). (Shareef et al., 2023) found that behavioural intention of using AI is backed up by user trust but (Dinh & Park, 2023) brought out a new perspective of use of fear to influence intention to use. (Asante et al., 2023) advanced the understanding of how consumers engagement with AI technologies in e-commerce by introduction social comparison. The second most prominent variables group was consumer related variables which included online customer experience and customer satisfaction. (S. C. Silva et al., 2023) discussed various factors which are essential to provide a better customer experience in an online environment. Other variables studies were trust related, organization related and AI type relate. (Table 9)

Mediators

The authors analysed the literatures and identified multiple factors that facilitate the application of AI in E-commerce. The most prominent mediators were AI attributes related variable and trust related variables. Trust related variables included consumer trust, perceived risk and trust variables. Trust is considered to be the most crucial antecedent of acceptance (Maglio et al., 2019) trust is user's belief that the agent will collect and use information appropriately reducing risk (Rohden & Zeferino, 2023) Trust promotes positive attitude towards the agent (Luo et al., 2023). AI attribute related variables included perceived anthropomorphism, social presence and other. Social presence is the extent to which psychological presence of the agent is implied (Dinh & Park, 2023) and anthropomorphic attributes are the human like traits exhibited by the agent (Epley et al., 2007). (Malhotra & Ramalingam, 2023) also confirmed the mediating effect of anthropomorphism. (Table 9)

Moderators

The researchers found various moderators that either amplify or reduce the impact. The most prominent moderators explored were consumer related, demographics related and trust related. Regarding demographics related – gender is the most explored variable. (Luo et al., 2023) found that women are more cautious and quickly persuaded by perceived risks, men are more task-oriented and easily influenced by performance and utility. (Ben Saad & Choura, 2023) found that men have perceive higher enjoyment than women. Regarding consumer related variables – (Yoon & Lee, 2021) found that individual with higher need for cognition can be persuaded with the AI personalization quality whereas individuals with low level of cognition will focus on technology quality. (Table 9)

VARIABLE	FRQ	EXAMPLES	ARTICLES
INDEPENDENT VARIABLES			
AI attributes related	13	perceived anthropomorphism chatbot attributes, perceived warmth, perceived competence, AI information quality, e service quality, perceived intelligence, perceived usefulness	(Chen et al., 2023; Cheng, Bao, et al., 2022; Malhotra & Ramalingam, 2023; Moussawi et al., 2021S. C. Silva et al., 2023)
trust related	11	perceived trust, security, perceived risk, perceived privacy	(Bedue & Fritzsche, 2022; Cadieux et al; Roh et al., 2023; Rohden & Zeferino, 2023)
consumer related	9	confirmation of expectation, effort expectancy, social influence, attitude	(de Andres-Sanchez & Geneffort Albesa, 2023; Wannner et al., 2022)
AI type related	4	virtual recommendation agent, service agent type, Assistant type	(Asante et al., 2023; Ben Saad & Choura, 2023; Pizzi et al., 2021; Song, Xing, et al., 2022)
DEPENDENT VARIABLES			

Intention/ Engagement	29	Adoption, behavioural intention, engagement, word of mouth, purchase intention, online shopping intention	(Moussawi et al., 2021; Rahman et al., 2021; Song, Xing, et al., 2022; Bedue & Fritzsche, 2022; de Andres-Sanchez & Gene-Albesa, 2023; Toubes et al., 2021; Wanner et al., 2022)
Consumer Related	5	online customer experience, customer satisfaction,	(S. C. Silva et al., 2023; (Cheng, Bao, et al., 2022; Brill et. al (2020)
Trust & Risk Related	4	risk to privacy perception, trust, loyalty	Rohden & Zeferino, 2023; Nilanshi et al. (2015; (Chen et al., 2023) Moriuchi, E. (2019)
Organization Related	4	CRM performance, company competitive advantage	(Behera et al., 2022; (L. Li et al., 2023) Dymitrowski &Mielcarek (2021)
AI Related	4	recommender system types, digital innovation, user compliance	Song et al. (2023; Adam et. al (2021)

MEDIATORS

AI Related	10	perceived animacy, perceive intelligence, perceived performance expectancy, social presence, perceived communication quality	(Malhotra & Ramalingam, 2023; Roh et al., 2023; Song, Xing, et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2022)
Consumer /Perception Related	8	Attitude, perceived enjoyment, psychological engagement, perceived effort expectancy, consumer emotions	(Asante et al., 2023; Rahman et al., 2021; Roh et al., 2023; Yoon & Lee, 2021)
Trust Related	7	consumer trust, perceived risk, perceived transparency	Xu et al. (2023), (Luo et al., 2023; Roh et al., 2023)

MODERATORS

Consumer Related	9	Experience, need for human interaction, need for cognition, consumer knowledge, fear of	(Adam et al., 2021; Dinh & Park, 2023; Nguyen et al., 2022; Song, Xing, et al., 2022)
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COVID 19		
Risk/ Trust Related	6	trust in AI, perceived risk, information privacy concerns (Ben Saad & Choura, 2023; Brill et al., 2019; Malhotra & Ramalingam, 2023; Saleem et al., 2023)
Demographic Related	6	Gender, generational cohort, age (Kim et al., 2023; Wanner et al., 2022)
Others	4	task complexity, product type, level of robot intelligence (Cheng, Bao, et al., 2022; Song, Du, et al., 2022)

Table 9 Characteristics

Methodology

What is methodology, Table (10) presents the data collection method and table (11) presents the data analysis method employed in the sample publications. The researcher found that quantitative methods were preferred over qualitative methods. The researches were mostly empirical except for few which were conceptual. The sample publications also included review papers, case studies and scale development. The most prominent method of data collection was survey followed by experiments. In terms of data analysis method PLS SEM followed by structural equation modelling were the most dominant methods of analysis preferred. The other prominent methods were regression analysis, Hayes process, data mining techniques and parametric tests.

DATA COLLECTION	FRQ	Examples
Quantitative Studies		
Survey	42	(Xu et al. (2023; Brill et. al., 2020; Moriuchi. E., 2019; Hasiao et al., 2019; Rudko et al., 2021; Song et al., 2023; Chow et al., 2023; Dymitrowski &Mielcarek 2021; Pelau et al.,2021)
Experiment	11	(Ben Saad & Choura, 2023; Guo & Jiang, 2023; Liao & Sundar, 2022; Pizzi et al., 2021; Shareef et al., 2023; Song, Du, et al., 2022; Xie et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2022)
QUALITATIVE STUDIES		
Case Study	5	(Koponen & Rytsy, 2020; Saura et al., 2023; S. C. Silva et al., 2023; Wei & Pardo, 2022)

Review	8	(Rodrigues et al., 2022; Bai & Li, 2022; Kiani Mavi et al., 2022; Leong et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2020; Bandara et al., 2020; Thomas et al., 2023; Ariza-Garzon et al., 2021; Thiebes et al., 2021)
Descriptive	7	Qin & Jiang 2019; Hoyer et al., 2020; (Hoyer et al., 2020; Shang & Kauffman, 2020; Wing et al., 2021; Zhang & Yue, 2020)
Mixed	4	(Salminen et al., 2022; Hsu et al., 2021; Lee & Kim, 2022; Moussawi et al., 2021; Rohden & Zeferino, 2023)
Scale Development	1	Özkanlısoy et al. (2022)

Table 9. Data Collection Methods

DATA ANALYSIS	FRQ	CIATION
Pls Sem	20	(de Andres-Sanchez & Gene-Albesa, 2023; Lee & Kim, 2022; L. Li et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2023; Saleem et al., 2023; F. A. Silva et al., 2023)
SEM	9	(Moriuchi, E., 2019; Song et al., 2023; Chow et al., 2023; Nayal et al., 2022)
Regression Analysis,	7	(Xu et al.,2023; Adam et al.,2021; Pelau et al.,2021)
Correlation Analysis	2	(Xu et al., 2023; Hsu et al., 2021; Lin & Li, 2023)
Data Mining Techniques	4	(Saura et al., 2021; Saura et al., 2023; Trivedi et al., 2022)
T-Test	4	(Dymitrowski &Mielcarek 2021; Guo & Jiang, 2023; E. S. Silva & Bonetti, 2021)
Hayes Process	3	(Liao & Sundar, 2022; Malhotra & Ramalingam, 2023; Pizzi et al., 2021)
ANOVA	3	(Hsu et al., 2021; Liao & Sundar, 2022; E. S. Silva & Bonetti, 2021)
Chi Square Test	3	Moriuchi, E. (2019), Dymitrowski &Mielcarek (2021)
Thematic Analysis	3	(Bandara et al.,2020; Koponen & Rytsy, 2020; Yoon & Lee, 2021)
Content Analysis	2	(Nichifor et al., 2021), (Rohden & Zeferino, 2023)
Multiple Group Analysis	1	(Kim et al., 2023)

Multiple Correspondence Analysis	1	Rudko et al. (2021)
Spatial Data Analysis	1	(Matuszelanski & Kopczewska., 2022)
Discriminant Validity	1	(Pizzi et al., 2021)
MANOVA	1	(Pizzi et al., 2021)
Fuzzy-Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis	1	(Hsu et al., 2021)
Shapiro- Wilk Test	1	(Guo & Jiang, 2023)

Table 9 Data Analysis Techniques

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the researchers performed a bibliometric and TCCM analysis on AI in E-commerce through 112 publications indexed in WoS. The study followed the PRISMA inclusion exclusion criteria along with framework- based review, and analysed the results through R bibliometric package, VOS viewer and Microsoft Excel.

The first research question (RQ1) related to the trend and prominent journals, articles authors, affiliations and countries were addressed by performance analysis. The researchers found that the field of AI in E-commerce has acknowledged a sudden growth in publications and citations from 2019 & 2020 respectively. Countries like China, USA and India have published the most articles and Pusan National University proved to be the most productive university of this domain. The *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research* was found to be the most prominent journal with highest number of publications. In terms of authors Jian Mou was found to be the most productive author with highest publication but in terms of citations Adam Martin’s article “*AI Based Chatbots in Customer Service and Their Effects on User Compliance*” was the most cited article with 182 citations.

The second research question (RQ2) related to the key concepts and trending keywords of this field. Keyword co-occurrence analysis was conducted which revealed that artificial intelligence, e-commerce, trust, Covid-19, chatbot, machine learning, personalization, innovation and digitalization are the key topics which are being studied in this field. The third research question (RQ3) was related to the intellectual structure which was addressed by conducting co-citation analysis. The analysis revealed four leading research fronts: Artificial Intelligence Marketing: role, Technology acceptance: Integration of Theories and Methodology, AI and trust and Future Perspectives in Artificial Intelligence Research.

The fourth research question (RQ) is related to investigating the sample publications to find the prominent theories and variables, most researchers industry and county and most used methodology. The investigation was also used to give future research directions. The analysis revealed UTAUT model is the most prominent theory applied to this field and Chinese population has been researches mostly. In terms of industry tourism and hospitality has been studied the most and in terms of methodology SEM and PLS SEM are the most prominent methods. The organizational perspective has not been researched a lot which leaves a gap open for future researches.

RESEARCH IMPLICATION

Businesses are continuously investing in AI-based technologies, and because of the way these innovations are altering the marketing world, there is a rapid increase in interest in this area for research (**Dwivedi et al., 2019**). The growth of publications demands for analysis and synthesis of literatures. Thus, the study comprehensively evaluated the literatures on AI in E-commerce. The paper examines the literatures from 2001 -2023 using bibliometric analysis. The bibliometric results underline the rise in publications, key trends, topics studies and clusters which would aid interested researchers in identifying research gaps. The TCCM framework draws attention to the conceptual gaps in theories, context, characteristics, and methods that could improve the field as a whole.

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

The authors conducted an integrated bibliometric and TCCM framework analysis of sample publications AI in E-commerce and on the basis of the analysis following are the future research directions suggested. (Table 10)

FUTURE RESEARCH RECOMMENDATIONS

THEORY	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Exploring the currents multidisciplinary theories in context of AI in E-commerce.2. Developing new theories in context to this domain.3. Adopt theories in use approach to conduct researches.4. Employ adoption theories such as (Roh et al., (2023)), trust related theories, cognitive theories and also various multidisciplinary theories.
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CONTEXT

1. Countries like USA, Brazil, India, Spain and Germany have few number publications therefore, researchers can further explore fresh possibilities in these countries.
2. Since business have crossed the geographical boundaries Cross culture researches can be conducted
3. Further researches can be industry focused researches to get depth insights of the requirements and potential of different industries.

CHARACTERISTICS

1. Application of new and current AI types in the field of e-commerce and be explored by the researchers.
2. What attributes of AI affects its acceptance and reuse can be further explored by the researchers.
3. The organizational aspect of uses of AI in e-commerce is underexplored which may be studied in future.
4. Variables that contribute to the improvement of customer experience while using AI may prove to be an emerging topic for future.
5. Robots are being used to do work, how the level of intelligence expected by the user influences their use has only been explored by (31), which leaves the academia world with a gap too be bridged.

METHODS

1. Future researches can utilize analytical tools such as data mining, content analysis, bootstrap and thematic analysis.
2. Future researches can focus on scale development for variables related to this domain.
3. Future researches can adopt experimental methods to develop a better understanding of user responses.

Table 10 Future Research Recommendations

LIMITATIONS

The authors made every effort to fully explore the subject, however this study has certain limitations. First, we adopted a vigorous keyword search for the study but we might have missed literatures related to AI in e-commerce. Secondly the data was extracted only from WoS database, few articles that aren't available on WoS may have been omitted which can be incorporated in future researches using other databases. Third, the study employed VOS viewer and R Biblioshiny package for bibliometric analysis future researches can employ

diverse software and advance machine learning tools. Besides these limitations our research contributes by adding to the knowledge of this domain, the progressive growth of AI in E-commerce and also provides future research recommendations.

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